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Abstract. The article contains information about the methods, principles and their content of studying foreign languages today, as well as the importance of the approaches used in studying modern languages for the educational process.

Keywords. Foreign languages, Aspect principle, Method, Structure principle, "Transformation principle", "Ideographic grammar direction", "Functional structure principle", "Interactive teaching", "Application of technologies", "Communicative approach".

Introduction

The practical importance of language in society is extremely great, therefore, in each country, serious attention is paid to the issues of teaching and learning languages, including the problems of the effectiveness of learning foreign languages.

As is known, as a result of the consistent reforms being carried out in the field of education in our republic, education in general secondary schools is conducted in 7 languages: Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Turkmen.

From a historical point of view, language is a powerful force that has created not only a person, but also human society, has caused its development, and even today connects different countries with each other. Therefore, great attention is paid to the development of the most effective approaches and intensive methods of learning foreign languages. Approaches and methods of teaching foreign languages in the education system are improving.

However, the concepts of approach, principle, method used in teaching foreign languages are often used interchangeably with the concepts of method and methods in practice, that is, they are used both to determine the principle direction of teaching and in the sense of teaching method. In fact, "Method is derived from the Greek word methods - which means a method of research, a way. Also, when interpreting the word method in a broad sense, it is manifested as follows:

1. A method of knowing and studying natural and social phenomena,
2. Method, style;

The term methodology is derived from the Greek word methodika and "The word methodical means a method and a method, methods". In a broad sense, it is interpreted as follows:

- A set of methods and methods for performing, implementing, and completing a task.
- The doctrine of teaching methods[1].

In the study of foreign languages, "problem-based learning", "technologies", "dialogical approach", "audiovisual", "visual", "brainstorming", "project method" are considered to be highly effective methods[7].

In society, the study of foreign languages is mainly focused on issues of speech, dialogue, and communication. A number of principles are also formed directly in the study of foreign languages. The meaning of the word principle is a doctrine, the main, primary rule of worldview, priority ideas, and the main direction of practical activity[8]. The following are indicated as the most active principles in the study of foreign languages[2]:

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1. The principle of aspects. This principle recommends studying the language in three aspects based on its structure: phonetic, lexical, and grammatical aspects.

2. The principle of structure. This principle was put forward by one of the prominent representatives of American structuralism, Ch. Frieze, whose main idea was to study languages comparatively according to their structure and develop models that differ in both languages, and then, based on these models, to form the skills of speaking in a foreign language.

3. The principle of aspectual structure. This principle is also called the “new aspect”. One of its founders, I.V. Rakhmanov, based on the unity of language and speech, distinguishes 4 speech units (simple sentences, simple sentences with an introductory phrase, compound sentences and interrogative sentences) and develops speech models related to their use.

4. The principle of transformation. American linguists Z. Harris, F. French, N. Chomsky propose learning to express thoughts based on the selection of patterns existing in each language and their transformation through this principle.

5. The principle of functional structure. This principle is based on the idea of transitioning from content to its forms of expression, and the need to study speech models to show different forms of expressing thoughts in a particular situation is put forward.

6. The direction of ideographic grammar. This direction, which emerged in the 80s in Russian linguistics, proposes the idea of semantizing grammar in order to strengthen the connection between lexis and grammar, which is necessary for both theory and practice in teaching Russian as a second language. In this case, the language learner is encouraged to find the means of expression (symbols) to express his/her thoughts based on communicative goals, that is, to move from content to form, using the methodology[3].

7. Communicative principle. Proponents of this principle recommend linking knowledge related to the grammatical structure of the language to a specific situation, and using conditional speech exercises to form grammatical skills[4].

The question arises as to what is the importance of the concept of approach in learning foreign languages. In this context, what is an approach? Approach is a way of looking at teaching and learning. The answer to the question of what a language is and how to learn it is found on the basis of any language teaching approach.

Today, modern approaches to teaching foreign languages are considered as a factor that helps to make the language learning process effective and interesting, and the following approaches have been distinguished by their effectiveness[9]:

1. Communicative approach - in this approach, the first goal in learning foreign languages is communication. Students learn through tasks aimed at using the language they are learning in real-life situations. This method gives them the opportunity to freely and correctly express their thoughts and communicate with representatives of other nationalities.

2. Interactive teaching - this approach is focused on the active participation of students, who play roles in groups, hold discussions. This method allows them to exchange ideas and use the language in practice.

3. Use of technology - in the modern teaching process, advanced technologies, namely the Internet and mobile communication devices, can make learning more interesting. The rational use of online resources, interactive games, video and audio materials, for example, Duolingo, Quizlet, and other platforms, helps to interest students in learning a language. These modern approaches not only

help to increase the efficiency of teaching and learning foreign languages, but also turn students into actively motivated students.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that learning foreign languages, including Russian, has been recognized among young people as a great step towards world knowledge and is highly valued as the key to all knowledge.

Nowadays, learning and teaching foreign languages is considered an integral part of our lives, and knowledge of foreign languages guarantees priority in all areas and success. After all, learning a foreign language is a requirement of today, a requirement of the times.

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